

UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS FOR OPTICAL PERMEABILITY MEASUREMENT OF REINFORCING TEXTILES

E. Fauster^{1*}, H. Grössing², R. Schledjewski^{1,2}

¹ Chair of Processing of Composites,
Department Polymer Engineering and Science,
Montanuniversität Leoben, Leoben, Austria,

² Christian Doppler Laboratory for High Efficient Composite Processing,
Montanuniversität Leoben, Leoben, Austria,

* Corresponding author (ewald.fauster@unileoben.ac.at)

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1 Introduction

Liquid composite molding (LCM) represents a group of processing methods, which have in common that a dry preform of reinforcing textiles is placed in a mold and then impregnated with the liquid polymer matrix material. The impregnation process plays a key role as insufficiently saturated regions directly affect the mechanical properties of the final component. In order to avoid elaborate and expensive impregnation trials for finding the optimal impregnation strategy, filling simulations can be accomplished. This type of simulation is based on permeability values characterizing the resistance of the reinforcing textile structures for being impregnated with the matrix material. In order to provide meaningful simulation results, reliable permeability values are required.

Parameter studies addressing the permeability of reinforcing structures show a significant level of uncertainty associated with the permeability values. Of course, the reinforcing material itself represents the main source of uncertainty due to inhomogeneous material parameters [1–7], but also inappropriate handling of the reinforcing structure can give a strong influence [8]. Nonetheless, there is a contribution to the overall uncertainty caused by the measurement system itself. In this work, a 2-dimensional optical permeability measurement system is investigated with respect to the inherent measurement uncertainty. For this analysis, the measurement system itself is presented together with the digital image processing algorithm used to determine the timely advancement of the flow front during the experiment. Moreover, the procedure for calculating the permeability tensor values out of these characteristics is briefly described. Finally, a specific type of radial flow experiment is presented, that can be used to derive the measurement

uncertainty associated with the permeability tensor components.

2 Basics and Background

2.1 Darcy's Law and the 2D-Permeability Tensor

The process of impregnating a dry preform of reinforcing textiles with liquid matrix material can be understood as saturating a porous structure with a viscous liquid. Following Darcy's law [9], the flow characteristics can mathematically be described according to:

$$v = -\frac{1}{\eta} K \nabla p. \quad (1)$$

Therein, the fluid flow velocity vector $v \left[\frac{m}{s} \right]$ is related with the driving pressure gradient $\nabla p \left[\frac{N}{m^2 m} \right]$ through the fluid viscosity $\eta \left[\frac{Ns}{m^2} \right]$ and the permeability of the reinforcing structure, described by the permeability tensor $K [m^2]$.

Considering the flow of a liquid polymer in a planar reinforcing textile structure, the 2-dimensional permeability tensor shows the following general structure:

$$K_{[2 \times 2]} = \begin{bmatrix} k_x & k_{xy} \\ k_{yx} & k_y \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

By choosing an appropriate coordinate frame (or by application of a coordinate transformation), the primary flow directions can be aligned with the coordinate frame of the measurement system. This leads to a simplification of the permeability tensor:

$$K_{[2 \times 2]} = \begin{bmatrix} k_x & 0 \\ 0 & k_y \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

with k_x and k_y denoting the permeability values along the primary flow directions.

2.2 Determination of Permeability Values

Basically, permeability measurement is accomplished in a two-step procedure:

1. the actual saturation experiment, i.e. determination of the timely advancement of the fluid impregnating the reinforcing structure, and
2. calculation of the permeability tensor components from these characteristics following a specific mathematical algorithm.

A couple of different approaches are existing for performing the experimental part of the procedure, the best known of them being based on optical and capacitive measurement principles, respectively [10]. Comparing these two approaches, the capacitive measurement system is advantageous in terms of robustness and stiffness of the metal mold halves. Thus, it allows for measurements in wider areas of injection pressure and temperature. The optical approach is beneficial as the timely advancement of the liquid flow front can be visually observed during the experiment and the number of data points used to characterize the flow front is significantly higher than with a capacitive system. This enables the fluid flow front to be reconstructed during the saturation experiment at a higher level of detail.

For the calculation of the permeability tensor components by means of the timely characteristics of the flow front advancement, a number of different approaches are reported in the literature. All of these algorithms share the need for finding a solution of the second-order differential equation describing the 2-dimensional pressure distribution $p(x, y)$ of the fluid impregnating the anisotropic reinforcing structure:

$$\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} + \alpha \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial y^2} = 0. \quad (4)$$

Thereby, $\alpha = \frac{k_y}{k_x}$ denotes the degree of anisotropy of the reinforcing structure. Adams and Rebenfeld [11] presented an algorithm, which is based on an iterative numerical solution for the degree of anisotropy α . Chan and Hwang [12] on the contrary described an approach which introduces a transformation of the anisotropic problem into an equivalent isotropic system (EIS). Thereby, the second-order differential equation simplifies to the well-known Laplace equation [9; 13; 14], for which a closed form solution exists. The resulting isotropic

permeability is finally transformed back to the anisotropic system in order to obtain the desired values for k_x and k_y , respectively. As a result of the low requirements on computational power, the latter approach is used for the permeability calculations in the work presented in this paper.

3 Optical Permeability Measurement

3.1 Measurement Principle

The basic principle of the optical permeameter measurement system investigated in this work has originally been presented by Adams et al. [15] and is termed "radial flow experiment". In Fig. 1, a scheme of the setup is shown. The measurement system consists of a mould which is composed of a metal bottom half and a top half built from a glass plate. In between the two halves of the mold, a metal frame with distinct thickness is positioned. The latter hardware component is termed "cavity frame", as its inner cutting dimensions and thickness specify the volume to be filled with the fluid during the experiment, i.e. the mold cavity.

For the actual experiment, layers of the reinforcing textiles to be analyzed are placed inside the cavity, which is subsequently filled with a liquid through a central injection point in the metal bottom half of the mold. During the radial flow experiment, an image sequence is acquired with a camera system positioned above the mold. The camera focusses through the glass plate onto the upper surface of the reinforcing textiles placed inside the cavity. By analysis of the acquired sequence images, the timely advancement of the fluid flow front can be determined.

3.2 Test Rig

Fig. 2 shows a picture of the test rig used for the radial flow experiments described in this paper. The frame of the test rig is set up by standard aluminum profiles. Directly on top of the working table, the metal mold half is mounted. The security glass plate forming the upper mold half is made from two glass plates, each with a thickness of 20 mm, and a thin separating polymer foil. The glass mold half is framed with metal profiles in order to connect it to a hinge system on the back side of the test rig. A pneumatic cylinder finally provides for the flapping motion as indicated in Fig. 2. The actual mold cavity is specified through the cavity frame showing an inner dimension of 300 mm x 400 mm. After placing the reinforcing structures inside the cavity, the mold is closed by flapping the glass plate into a horizontal position. In addition, the glass plate is tightened with

the bottom mold half using a metal clamping frame and a set of screws. The radial flow experiment is then executed by injecting the test fluid into the cavity through a central injection point in the bottom metal mold half. Due to the thickness of the glass plate and the clamping frame used to tighten the glass plate, a maximum injection pressure of 6 bars can be applied.

At a distance of about 1 m above the mold, a camera system consisting of an industrial monochrome camera and a precision lens with a focal length of 16 mm is mounted. The camera is used to acquire an image sequence during the radial flow experiment at an acquisition rate of up to 50 fps at a resolution of 1392 x 1040 pixels. In order to determine the timely advancement of the fluid flow front, the sequence images are evaluated by means of a digital image processing algorithm specifically developed for this application. Each sequence image (see an exemplarily chosen image depicted in Fig. 3) is evaluated individually following a five-step procedure:

1. calculate the difference image with respect to a background image acquired at the beginning of the experiment in order to compensate for lighting variations during the experiment,
2. apply a binary mask image for segmentation of the relevant image regions inside the metal clamping frame (see Fig. 4),
3. threshold the masked difference image and apply morphological operations [16] in order to obtain a binary image of regions saturated by the fluid (see Fig. 5),
4. find sets of data points along the actual fluid flow front by image gradient methods, and
5. approximate an elliptical geometry model to the sets of data points (see Fig. 6) and calculate the major and minor axis lengths in order to obtain measures of the flow front extent along the principal flow directions.

The latter step is performed following an algorithm presented by O'Leary et al. [17] which minimizes the sum of the orthogonal distances of the data points to the elliptic geometry model in a least squares sense. As a result of evaluating the sequence images, the timely flow front advancement is obtained in terms of the major and minor axes length characteristics.

The test rig control task as well as the image and data acquisition, evaluation and storage tasks have been implemented in a LabView[®] application. More specifically, the acquired sequence images are evaluated online according to the image processing algorithm described above, i.e. at the same rate as the images are acquired. As a result, the timely flow front advancement is available immediately after finishing the radial flow experiment and the mathematical computation of the permeability tensor components can be accomplished instantaneously.

4 Experimental Work

4.1 Material and Experimental Parameters

The experiment described in the following section has been accomplished with a reinforcing structure exhibiting the following parameters:

- type of material: carbon fibre,
- type of fabric: biaxial non-crimped fabric with polyester stitching yarn,
- fibre orientation: 0°/90°,
- areal weight: 565 g/m².

Furthermore, the fluid utilized for the radial flow experiment was standard edible oil with a red colored additive required for establishing sufficiently high contrast between unsaturated and saturated image regions. The viscosity of the injected fluid was measured with a rotational rheometer and showed 65 mPas. Finally, the following experimental parameters have been chosen:

- cavity height: 3,5 mm,
- number of layers: 6 mm,
- resulting fibre volume content: 54,4 %,
- fluid injection pressure: 1 bar.

4.2 Repeatability Experiment

Permeability values reported in the literature [1; 8] show a significant level of uncertainty with major contributions from inhomogeneities in the reinforcing materials. Nonetheless, the measurement system itself also accounts for a certain portion. In order to estimate the contribution of the optical measurement system presented in Section 3.2 on the overall uncertainty associated with the resulting permeability tensor components, a repeatability analysis has been carried out.

The analysis is based on a single radial flow experiment, which has been conducted according to the scheme described in Section 3.1. After placing the layers of reinforcing materials inside the mold cavity, the fluid injection has been started together with the acquisition of the image sequence. During the timely advancement of the flow front, the fluid injection has been interrupted at certain stages of the experiment. However, the acquisition of the image sequence has been pursued and as a result, the radial extent of the elliptic flow front has been acquired virtually at repeatability conditions during these stages of interrupted fluid injection.

5 Results

5.1 Statistical Data Analysis

The procedure described in Section 4.2 has been repeated five times over the entire length of the experiment and for all of the five sections, a number of about 800 images (and thus, measurement values) have been acquired. The timely characteristics of the major and minor axis length obtained by evaluation of the sequence images throughout this experiment are depicted in Fig. 7. Therein, the five sections of nearly constant major and minor axis length reflecting the periods of interrupted fluid injection are highlighted. These five sections have subsequently been analyzed in terms of their statistical nature.

At first, slight rises in the major and minor axes lengths have been observed in all of the five sections. These can be explained by capillary actions taking place during the periods of interrupted fluid injection. However, the rises show nearly linear characteristics. Thus, a simple strategy has been applied in order to compensate for these drifts: A linear regression model has been approximated to the measurement values and the deviations of the measurement values from the regression line are used for the further steps of the analysis.

For each of the five sections, the statistical nature of the measurement data has been verified to follow a Gaussian probability density function by means of Lilliefors tests [18]. As these tests have been passed successfully, histogram plots have been generated for the data derived for the five sections of interrupted fluid injection. The histogram plots are depicted in Fig. 8, Fig. 9, Fig. 10, Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 together with exemplarily chosen corresponding sequence images. Moreover, the most important parameters describing the statistical nature of the data, i.e. average values and standard deviation values, have been computed. The values

obtained are listed in Table 1. Therein, $\mu_{\text{Maj},i}$ and $\mu_{\text{Min},i}$ denote the average values of major and minor axis length for the i^{th} section, respectively, whereas $\sigma_{\text{Maj},i}$ and $\sigma_{\text{Min},i}$ term the corresponding standard deviation values. As can be seen, the standard deviation values are varying between 0,05 mm and 0,11 mm for the minor axis length as well as between 0,07 mm and 0,28 mm for the major axis length.

The standard deviation values of the first two sections of interrupted fluid injection are nearly constant and in this characteristic, they are deviating from the trend to be observed for the remaining three sections. There, the standard deviation values clearly increase with the flow front advancement. At first glance, this appears to be surprising as with increasing radial flow front extent, the number of data points available for approximating the elliptical geometry model increases as well. Thus, stronger averaging effects inherent to approximating the elliptical geometry model can be expected. However, the reason for this trend is rather to be found in the reinforcing material itself. With increasing radial extent of the flow front, the number of intersecting positions between flow front and stitching yarn (which is used for fixation of the carbon fibre rovings to form the biaxial non-crimped fabric) increases as well. At these intersection points, the flow front can be observed to advance in leaps rather than continuously.

5.2 Uncertainty Propagation

Based on the standard deviation values resulting from the experiment described above, the uncertainty associated with the permeability tensor components characterizing the reinforcing structure has been estimated. For that purpose, a Monte-Carlo analysis based on artificial sets of data has been performed.

The timely characteristics of major and minor axis lengths as shown in Fig. 13 have been used as vectors of mean data required for this analysis. These characteristics have been obtained in a representative radial flow experiment using the same material and experimental parameters as listed in Section 4.1. Moreover, the covariance matrices associated with the vectors of mean data have been set up based on the standard deviation values obtained in the statistical data analysis described in Section 5.1.

Based thereupon, a set of $n = 1000$ artificial timely characteristics of major and minor axis length values have been created. As a result of the underlying

covariance matrices, these timely characteristics follow the statistical nature of the data obtained in the repeatability experiment. Finally, all of these sets have been evaluated according to the mathematical scheme proposed in Section 2.2. As a result, a number of n permeability values k_x and k_y respectively, are obtained. For these results, again the average and standard deviation values, denoted with μ_{k_x} and μ_{k_y} as well as σ_{k_x} and σ_{k_y} , respectively, are computed. The permeability values ultimately found are specified as follows:

$$k_x = \mu_{k_x} \pm \sigma_{k_x} = 2,97 \cdot 10^{-11} \pm 1,56 \cdot 10^{-15} \text{ m}^2, \quad (5)$$

$$k_y = \mu_{k_y} \pm \sigma_{k_y} = 1,58 \cdot 10^{-11} \pm 0,47 \cdot 10^{-15} \text{ m}^2. \quad (6)$$

6 Summary, Conclusions and Outlook

6.1 Summary

In the present paper, the measurement uncertainty inherent to an optical system for determining 2-dimensional permeability values of reinforcing structures is estimated. The approach of optical permeability measurement has been outlined and the test rig used for the experiments presented in this paper has been described.

Following a specific radial flow experiment superimposed with a number of sections of interrupted fluid injection, the statistical nature as well as the uncertainty associated with the measurement results, i.e. the timely advancement of radial flow front extent has been determined.

Lastly, the uncertainty associated with the permeability values characterizing the reinforcing structure has been derived by means of a Monte-Carlo analysis based on artificially created data sets.

6.2 Conclusions

The major output of the work presented in this paper is seen in the procedure to follow in order to estimate the measurement uncertainty inherent to an optical permeameter system.

In addition, the results obtained indicate that the contributions of the measurement system itself to the uncertainty associated with the determined permeability values are negligibly small.

6.3 Outlook and Future Work

Additional experiments based on the procedure presented in this paper incorporating other types of reinforcing structures as well as varying

experimental parameters are suggested in order to give to a more general statement about the results. Moreover, the statistical uncertainty analysis can be extended by estimating the influence of material parameters showing a stochastic nature, e.g. the areal weight of the fabrics, on the resulting permeability values. Finally, an overall examination of the optical permeability measurement system incorporating sources of statistical as well as systematic errors is proposed as future work.

Fig. 1: Scheme of an optical permeability measurement system with its major hardware components.

Fig. 2: Optical permeability measurement system used for the radial flow experiments.

Fig. 3: Example sequence image acquired with the optical permeameter measurement system.

Fig. 5: Binary image computed by the image processing algorithm for finding the data points along the fluid flow front.

Fig. 4: Masked difference image highlighting the areas of the reinforcing textile saturated by the injected fluid.

Fig. 6: Sequence image with an overlay of the elliptic flow front model approximated to the sets of data points found along the fluid flow front.

Fig. 7: Timely advancement of the fluid flow front represented by the characteristics of major and minor axis lengths.

Fig. 8: First section of interrupted fluid injection: sequence image and histogram plots of major and minor axes lengths.

Fig. 9: Second section of interrupted fluid injection: sequence image and histogram plots of major and minor axes lengths.

Fig. 10: Third section of interrupted fluid injection: sequence image and histogram plots of major and minor axes lengths.

Fig. 11: Fourth section of interrupted fluid injection: sequence image and histogram plots of major and minor axes lengths.

Fig. 12: Fifth section of interrupted fluid injection: sequence image and histogram plots of major and minor axes lengths.

Fig. 13: Major and minor axes length determined in a representative radial flow experiment.

i	$\mu_{\text{Min},i}$ [mm]	$\sigma_{\text{Min},i}$ [mm]	$\mu_{\text{Maj},i}$ [mm]	$\sigma_{\text{Maj},i}$ [mm]
1	114,55	0,08	153,23	0,15
2	157,48	0,06	223,95	0,07
3	187,58	0,05	269,23	0,11
4	219,77	0,08	310,25	0,22
5	247,78	0,11	347,20	0,28

Table 1: Statistical parameters of major and minor axes length in the sections of interrupted fluid injection.

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